

THE HIDDEN AILMENTS: A DEEP DIVE INTO ANUKTA VYADHI***¹Dr. Ashwini Nayaka, ²Dr. Prashanth Baginoor**¹Asisstant Professor, ²Asisstant Professor¹Dept. of Roga Nidana Samata Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18093793>***Corresponding Author****Dr. Ashwini Nayaka**Asisstant Professor, Dept. of
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Kalaburgi 585302.**How to cite this Article:** *Dr. Ashwini Nayaka, Dr. Prashanth Baginoor. (2026). The Hidden Ailments: A Deep Dive Into Anukta Vyadhi. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 440-446. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.**INTRODUCTION**स्वस्थस्य स्वस्थ रक्षणं आतुरस्य विकार प्रशमणम् च //^[1]

Ayurveda strive for preventive aspects and helps in promotion and prolongation of healthy and happy life. To give relief to the patient the 4 pillars of *Ayurveda* is needed. It is told that a thorough knowledge about the *Shastra* is must for a good physician.

एकं शस्त्रस्त्रमधियानो न विधाच्छास्त्रनिज्यम्।^[2]

तस्मादबहूस्ःश्रुतः शास्त्रं विजनीयाचिकित्सकः॥

It is mentioned that whatever is available elsewhere is included in the *Samhitas*, and whatever is not available here cannot be found elsewhere.

यदिहास्ति तदन्यत्र यन्नेहास्ति न तत्क्वचित्।^[3]

अग्निवेशकृते तन्त्रे चरकप्रतिसंस्कृते॥

Even after saying this our *Acharyas* have not put any limitations for securing the knowledge from divergent roots. Emerging of new diseases make us to think little more while adopting the treatment modalities.

Here an attempt is made to understand some of the diseases through our literature.

- ADHISTHANA: *Adhithana* is the location in the body where the *dosh-dushya samurchana* take place, as the *dosha-dushya samurchana* can occur in any part of the body so identification of particular *Adhithana* is important.
- Basically there are two types of *Vyadhi* by *Adhithana Bheda* viz *Sharir* and *Manas*. But specific *Adhithana* in the body should be identify while diagnosing the disease.

- SAMUTTANA: The causative factors of the diseases. While studying *Anukta Vyadhi* causative factors[*Samuttana*] should be identify.

रोगमेकैक मेवं प्रकोपनणमेवंयोनि

मेवमुत्थानमेवमात्मानमेवमाधिष्ठान

मेवेदनमेवं संस्थानमेवंशब्दस्पर्शरूपरसगन्ध

मेवमुपद्रवमेवं वृद्धिस्थानक्षयसमन्वित मेवमुदर्क

मेवंनामानमेवंयोग विघात्//.^[8]

- Prakopana (Causative factors)
- Yoni (Dosha involvment)
- Uttana (Mode of manifestation)
- Atman (Pratyatma lakshana)
- Adhithana (Ashraya)
- Vedana (Nature of pain)
- Samsthana (Symptoms)

- Shabda, Sparsha, Roopa, Rasa, Gandha
- Upadrava (Complications)
- Vruddhi, Sthana, Kshaya (Aggravating and relieving factors)
- Udarka (Residual symptoms)
- Nama (Name of the disease)
- Yoga (Treatment)

Prakopana: The provoking factors are

Primary: Iodine deficiency

Autoimmune disease

Secondary: TSH deficiency

Yoni : The emergence of the disease by

Kapha and Vata

Uttana : The genesis of the disease is...

Atmana: The main features of the disease are

Fatigue

Weight gain

Adhithana : The site of presence of the disease...

Thyroid gland (Gala pradesha)

Vedana : The expression of pain like...

Muscle cramps and aches

Samsthana: It is identified through...

Symptoms	Dosha involved	Srotas
Fatigue	Vata, Kapha	Rasavaha
Weight gain	Kapha	Rasavaha, Medovaha
Cold intolerance	Vata, Kapha	Rasavaha
Dry skin	Vata	Rasavaha
Hair loss, brittle hairs	Vata	Asthivaha
Muscle pain	Vata	Asthivaha
Menstrual disturbance, Infertility	Vata	Arthavavaha, Shukravaha
Constipation	Vata	Purishavaha

Shabda, sparsha, roopa, rasa, gandha : The inspection of the disease...

Sparsha: Dry skin and dry hair

Shbda : poor hearing

Upadrava : The worsened condition of the disease shows...

- Atherosclerosis
- Heart attack
- Infertility
- Dysmenorrhea
- Goiter

Kshaya : The factors to provide relief are....

- Iodine rich diet
- Exercise

Vruddhi : The factors makes condition bad to worse...

- Alcohol and smoking
- Caffeine
- Goitrogenic food –cauliflower, cabbage etc
- Fat and processed food

Uadrka : The consequence of the disease...

- Hair loss
- Dry skin
- Obesity

Nama

आवृते श्लेमणोदने वैवर्ण्या वाकस्वरग्रहः।

दौर्बल्यं गुरुगान्त्रत्वमरुचिचोपजायते॥⁹

CONCLUSION

- Keeping one's own fund of knowledge, current is one of the Most formidable challenges that a physician faces.
- For staying current systematically and periodically search the literature for quality material related to annoying issues.
- In this regard *Tantrayukti*, *Anukta* and concept of *Anukta vyadhi* forms a bridge between the current issues and our literature.
- The breaking up of the intense bond of the component of pathogenesis is must, both in explained and unexplained categories of the diseases.
- Keeping this fundamental principle as a base, to un reveal the revealed matters in our language *Anukta* has got a great role.

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